

INFLUENCE OF INTERPHASE CHARACTERISTICS ON SHORT FIBER PLASTIC COMPOSITES

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Keywords: Interphase, Polymer-Matrix Composites, Nano-Indentation, Injection molding, Processing

ABSTRACT

Modern product development processes in mechanical engineering are governed of computer-aided finite-element (FE) simulations. To perform realistic FE simulations, the material behavior has to be described in an appropriate micromechanical material model. Therefore, the macroscopic behavior of a technical part can be described by using experimentally obtained information about the microstructure. Thus, an in-depth understanding of all underlying mechanisms and influences at microscale is required.

This contribution is focused on the characterization of the fiber-matrix interphase in short fiber reinforced plastics, which are used in numerous applications due to their versatility, rapid manufacturing capabilities, and tunable physical properties. The interphase is defined as the intersection region between the glass fiber and the polymer matrix where material properties differ from the bulk polymer. The presented results demonstrate that this region of less than 1 μm thickness has a major impact on the macroscale composite performance. At the same time, the distribution of local mechanical properties and the influence of processing on the interphase region are currently not understood. Therefore, this work aims for a systematic understanding of the interphase in order to obtain the influence of its local properties regarding the impact on the macroscale composite behavior. Herein, the interphase impact is characterized using a validated method from nanotribology. The macroscale composite properties are investigated by tension and inflation tests to link the resulting mechanical behavior with the local interphase configuration. In summary, the gain of information from the discovery to the manufacturing level could be used to increase the accuracy of FE simulations with an improved representation of fiber-matrix-interphase composites in material modeling.

1 INTRODUCTION

Short fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites are used in many applications. Different applications in the automotive or aviation industry benefit from the combination between a low density thermoplastic matrix and stiff short glass fibers to create high performance, lightweight parts. At macroscopic scale, the fibers are responsible for an increasing Young's modulus, representative for a higher stiffness, and a higher strength. At the microscale, the fibers transfer and carry the loads in the composite. Thus, the thermoplastic matrix defines the geometrical fiber position and transmits the load into the fibers. To achieve these functions, an optimized fiber-matrix interfacial region is critical.

Recent literature demonstrates the presence of a third phase in composites consisting of short glass fibers embedded in a soft polymer matrix [1]. Generally, this interphase region is defined as a region between the matrix and the inclusion with modified polymer properties [2]. The interphase property gradient and its extent are influenced in as yet unknown ways by the constituent chemistry, surface functional groups and processing conditions. Two significant formation mechanisms are identified from the literature: 1) The creation of an interphase is explained by interdiffusion processes at a macromolecular scale driven by thermodynamic forces [3]; 2) Semi-crystalline polymers contain spherulitic structures which are concentrated around the inclusion phase, where the inclusion acts as a nucleation agent [4]. The creation of a transcrystalline interphase around a fiber is presented in Fig. 1 by polarized light microscopy of a short fiber reinforced polypropylene [5]. The increased

concentration of spherulites around an inclusion should lead to modified mechanical material properties in this area. However, only the geometrical information and the interphase volume fraction for injection molded thermoplastic composites is available from experiments [1].

Figure 1: Evidence of an interphase: spherulitic structures are concentrated around the inclusion phase, which is acting as nucleation agent [5]

While short glass fiber composites produced by injection molding dominate the field of industrial composite materials [6], the analysis of injection molded short fiber composite specimen in terms of its interphase is lacking. The heat development during the injection of melted polymer influences the thermodynamic forces and interdiffusion processes which are responsible for the interphase creation. Consequently, this study examines the impact of the injection molding process and the importance of the fiber geometry and coatings on the creation of an interphase in semi-crystalline thermoplastic composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL FRAMEWORK

Early studies show that the fiber-matrix adhesion critically influences the entire composite behavior [7]. Additionally, preliminary results show that a fiber-matrix interphase can be geometrically identified for semi-crystalline short fiber reinforced thermoplastics [1]. However, no information about the mechanical properties of this interphase region is available in literature for these systems. Modern experimental tools allow an investigation of the identified intersection region towards improved mechanical composite properties. To achieve understanding of the impacts on the interphase requires extensive studies varying from microscale material effects to the processing and subsequent macroscale material behavior. The proposed contribution aims to link this microscale material characterization with the macroscale mechanical properties of plastic composites. Herein, the following three questions motivate the present study from the discovery to the manufacturing level:

1. What are the microscale influences for the formation of the interphase?
2. How can the mechanical properties of the interphase be accessed?
3. How does the interphase affect the macroscale composite behavior?

To answer the preceding questions, the presented work covers the micro- and macrostructural characterization of polymer composites with interphase. The entire framework is displayed in Fig. 2. Each section is dedicated to one of the addressed questions.

Figure 2: Framework of the study to characterize the influence of microscale interphase properties on the macroscopic mechanical behavior of plastic composites

On the microscale level, the influence of specific fillers or fiber coatings (sizing) is investigated based on different results in mechanisms and properties of polymer nanocomposites [8]. Filler geometries with various coatings are produced to analyze the impact of nucleation effects at the surface of the inhomogeneity. As control systems, amorphous polymers are examined for the matrix material to avoid crystallinity effects. For all mentioned parameters, different samples are produced by compounding and subsequent injection molding. The impact of the adjusted microstructural properties is validated by means of experimental characterization of the resulting interphase region. The nanotribological nano-scratch method is used to characterize the geometry of the interphase [1]. The developed methodology of nano-scratch on the described composite specimen differs from the so far published principles. Instead of using a constant normal scratch force like other authors, a constant indent depth over the scratch path is applied. This leads to several advantages as less material pile-up and the independency of the indenter geometry from the interphase thickness measurement. The typical scratch path between the matrix and the fiber with constant scratch depth is presented in Fig 3.

Figure 3: Nano-scratch from the matrix to the fiber with constant scratch depth

During the scratch procedure, the indenter tip crosses several layers with different material properties. To keep the scratch-depth at a constant level, the normal force is changed accordingly. In the case of no existing interphase, only one change of the slope between the matrix and the fiber would be detected. Through the observation of different slopes in the measured normal force, the determination of the interphase thickness is possible.

To investigate the influences of all microscale material modifications on the macroscale composite behavior, a specimen geometry and the related biaxial mechanical characterization test bench of short fiber reinforced plastics has been developed [9]. In this manner, different load cases can be realized as shown in Fig. 4. Using this experimental setup, the influence of local interphase characteristics on the mechanical properties of plastic composites is evaluated by means of the resulting stress-strain relationships.

Figure 4: Schematic view of the experimental setup and realized load cases

3 RESULTS AND SUMMARY

For the realization of the proposed research outline, several experimental methods must be applied. Generally, the proposed framework in Fig. 2 can be divided into the manufacturing part and the characterization of the interphase influence on mechanical properties.

Material and sample manufacturing: A semi-crystalline polybutylene terephthalate reinforced with 20 weight percent of short glass fibers (PBT-GF20) is chosen in this study. In recent work, a new specimen geometry for the biaxial mechanical characterization of short fiber reinforced thermoplastics as shown in Fig. 2 and 4 is introduced [10, 11]. The main feature of the specimen is a unidirectional fiber orientation in the measurement section. By unidirectional fiber orientation, the orientation of short fibers in one direction is understood. This is not to confound with laminates made of one or more unidirectional layers in endless fiber reinforced composites. The unidirectional fiber orientation in the present specimen can be explained with the high velocity of melt flow, which is induced by the sprue type and the decreasing cross-section of flow channel in the specimen geometry. Optical microscopy and computer tomography imaging techniques are validating the existence of a unidirectional fiber orientation in the central part of the specimen [9]. For the application of nano-scratch, a thin sample is milled out of the central tube section, dedicated for optical strain measurement as shown in Fig. 4. The specimens are produced with the injection molding machine “Allrounder 320c” by Arburg®.

Interphase influence on mechanical properties: To reproduce the preliminary results concerning the interphase thickness and the nano-scratch method, a Hysitron® TriboIndenter is used. In preliminary

tests, the influence of the scratch speed is analyzed based on literature values and finally kept at a constant value of 0.1 $\mu\text{m/s}$. A pre-scratch is performed with a constant normal depth of 100 nm over a scratch path from the matrix to the fiber. The realization of a scratch with a low penetration depth/force is a commonly applied method to reduce the influence of surface artefacts due to the foregoing polishing. Thus, surface roughness differences between matrix and fiber are excluded before the interphase identification. Subsequently, the main nano-scratch is performed with a constant normal depth of 150 nm. The length of the scratches is kept at 10 μm . For a representative measurement of the interphase depth, several fibers in the cutting plane are analyzed with identical parameters. The presence of these slopes can be explained with the identical situation as for constant scratch-depth in literature [12]: It becomes apparent that in case of constant normal scratch depth, the normal force shows different slopes at the intersection region between matrix and fiber. Therefore, the thickness of the fiber-matrix interphase can be evaluated.

As a conclusion of the conducted micro- and macroscale testing method, two representative results of the abovementioned experiments are presented in Fig. 5. The link between local fiber-matrix interphase properties and the macroscopic composite behavior is shown by means of the fiber coating and the processing parameters. In both studies, the procedure shown in Fig. 2 is applied. For each selected parameter the nano-scratch technique is applied to characterize the interphase thickness at microscale which is consequently compared with macroscale tensile tests. The influences of the fiber coating as well as the processing temperature on both micro- and macroscales are presented. The results in Fig. 5 (a) and (b) demonstrate a direct correlation between a higher interphase thickness and an improved macroscopic behavior.

Figure 5: Influences on the interphase thickness and the subsequent mechanical tensile properties of the composite: (a) Influence of the fiber coating (sizing), (b) Influence of the processing temperature

Fig. 5 (a) shows that uncoated fibers lead to a thinner interphase. The resulting lower adhesion between the matrix and the fibers explains the significant degradation (55 %) of the mechanical properties regarding the tensile strength. Thus, the macroscopic composite behavior depends strongly on the area of interest between the fiber and the matrix. Similarly in Fig. 5 (b), a change of the manufacturing temperature by a value of 30 K leads to increased interphase thickness and the mechanical properties are affected with a 23 % increase in the tensile strength.

4 CONCLUSION

In summary, the proposed framework provides an original approach based on the motivation to understand the link of local interphase characteristics at molecular scale to macroscale processing technology. As shown in Fig. 2, the output of the present contribution can be seen on the one hand in the understanding of local interphase characteristics aiming to improve the macroscale composite performance. On the other hand, macroscale testing evaluates the significance of local microstructural modifications regarding the mechanical properties of the composite material. For this reason, the resulting framework can be seen as a new interdisciplinary contribution to the research field of material science and engineering applications.

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